

THE ANTI-INTERLEUKIN-31 ANTIBODY LOKIVETMAB AS A NEW ADDITIONAL OPTION FOR CANINE ATOPIC DERMATITIS MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Background: The therapy and long term management of atopic dermatitis (AD) in dogs is a complex multicomponent process that may include various therapeutic modalities and approaches based on the various factors involved in the disease. There is no universal therapeutic plan for every patient with atopy. The multimodal approach may include local and systemic corticosteroids, cyclosporin, oclacitinib, medical bathing, local ceramides, allergen specific immunotherapy (ASIT) and Lokivetmab. Lokivetmab is a canine monoclonal antibody against interleukin (IL)-31. The unique design of anti-IL-31 antibody determines its high safety - Lokivetmab will work in all cases where pruritus is IL-31 related. Lokivetmab is an effective additional treatment option for the acute pruritus in dog with allergen specific immunotherapy (ASIT).

Objectives: The main objective of this study is to show that anti-IL-31 antibody can provide a rapid and effective reduction of pruritus in atopic dermatitis (AD) dogs that are being successfully managed through an ASIT protocol.

Animals: 9 dogs with AD on ASIT protocol.

Materials and Methods: Included in this study were 9 dogs with AD (n=9), aged between 2.5 and 7 years, that have presented in Multidisciplinary Veterinary Clinic Bulgaria between August 2024 and February 2025 with pruritus on ASIT protocol. All medical procedures were performed in accordance to animal welfare laws and regulations and with the written permission of the owners. Skin condition was monitored by surface cytology, while pruritus severity was assessed using the validated PVAS scale, and all dogs followed a standardized treatment protocol including ASIT and lokivetmab and parasite control, with exclusion of other systemic or topical therapies prior to evaluation.

Results: Skin cytology in all dogs revealed no bacteria, inflammatory cells, or yeast- excluding secondary microbial overgrowth as a cause of pruritus. Pruritus Visual Analog Scale (PVAS) scores showed a marked and rapid reduction in itching severity over time in most dogs, with pruritus reaching clinically controlled levels in the majority by day 7 and remaining stable through day 28. One dog exhibited persistent mild to moderate pruritus despite improvement in the group overall.

Conclusion: Lokivetmab has been established as a new additional option for reducing pruritus in episodes of increased pruritus in patient with AD successfully managed long-term with ASIT protocol.

Key words: Canine, Cytopoint, Lokivetmab, Anti-IL-31 antibody, AD therapy.

Introduction

According to the 2023 AD redefinition by the International Committee for Allergic Diseases of Animals (ICADA): „Canine atopic dermatitis is a hereditary, typically pruritic & predominantly T-cell driven inflammatory skin disease involving interplay between skin barrier abnormalities, allergen sensitisation & microbial dysbiosis.” (Eisenschenk *et al.* 2024). AD is a multifactorial disease, which management should include the following points: 1) correction of the barrier defect

(i.e. rehydration, which is best achieved with topical medications); 2) treatment of secondary bacterial or fungal infections; 3) antiallergic and/or anti-inflammatory therapy and/or antipruritic therapy (e.g. steroids, antihistamines, cyclosporine, oclacitinib, Lokivetmab (cytopoint), etc.); and 4) specific immunotherapy to restore Th2/Th1 imbalance. (Olivry *et al.* 2015). ASIT is a reliable, safe and modern approach to the long-term management of patients with atopic dermatitis. (Vacheva *et al.* 2023, Kasper *et al.* 2024). Identifying the specific allergens is crucial for managing the patients, their environment and therapy (Angarano et MacDonald 1991, DeBoer *et al.* 2017, Miller *et al.* 2012). Combining ASIT with other non-steroidal forms of therapy allows most patients to be controlled without long-term systemic glucocorticoids.

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Materials and Methods

Animals

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Skin cytology

For cytology Diff Quick type staining with Hemacolor Rapid kit, 111674001 (Merck) and Microscope Euromex Bio Blue (Netherland) were used. The cytology samples were examined in 10 oil-immersion fields.

Skin surface cytology was an important element in determining initially and monitoring during follow-up examinations the patients' skin condition. The results present important information essential information whether or not bacterial or yeast overgrowth was the cause of the itching.

Pruritus evaluation with PVAS-Pruritus Visual Analog Scale

In all 9 dogs, itching was assessed using the scale PVAS-Pruritus Visual Analog Scale (Hill, *et al.* 2007).

The PVAS reflects owners' perceptions of the level of itching in dogs. The PVAS is scale designed to measure the degree of itching in dogs, with the owner of the animal providing the main assessment, as they know their animal's behavior best in everyday life. The scale is a straight horizontal line 10 cm long (or marked from 0 to 10) on which the owner notes the level of itching of the dog over the past 24 hours or days. A value of 0 means "no itching", and a value of 10 means "unbearable itching, in which the dog cannot sleep, eat or rest. Owners also cannot get away from their dog's itching". This is a very sensitive scale, which is directly related to the severity of the disease and the animal's quality of life. In dogs with atopic dermatitis, the PVAS is used both in the diagnostic process and in monitoring the effectiveness of treatment. In clinical practice, a PVAS score below 2 is often considered to indicate adequately controlled itching, while scores above 5 or 6 indicate active and severe itching requiring therapeutic intervention. Changes of 2 or more points in the PVAS are considered clinically significant, especially when assessing the effect of therapy.

By regularly completing the scale, the veterinarian can monitor the dynamics of the condition and compare the effect of different therapies in an objective framework based on the owner's observations. The PVAS is easy to use, does not require specialised training, and is accepted as a reliable and validated tool in diseases in which itching is the main symptom, especially in atopy (Hill *et al.* 2007, Meichner *et al.* 2019).

Medication history and subsequent therapy

In all 9 animals, concomitant medical therapy met the following:

Application of Lokivetmab (Cytoint, Zoetis) (2 mg/kg) s.c- Day 0 (Fleck *et al.*, 2021). All dogs received Isoxazoline product for parasite control (used in the last minimum 12 months); In the last 11 months or more all dogs received ASIT protocol (NEXT MUNE).

The following medications such as: injectable corticosteroids (Long/short acting), Janus kinase inhibitors, Cyclosporine, oral corticosteroids, oral and injectable antibiotics, antifungal drugs – have not been used in recent 4 weeks. Topical steroids (skin/otic), shampoos, foam, creams, ointments, sprays - have not been used in recent 2 weeks.

Results

Cytology Results

9/9 dogs on skin cytology did not demonstrate the presence of neutrophils and other inflammatory cells, bacteria and east.

Pruritus evaluation with PVAS-Pruritus Visual Analog Scale

Table 1: PVAS of Patients 9 dogs (P1-P9) on Day 0, 3, 7, 14, 21, 28.

PVAS	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9
Day 0	8	8	9	9	9	8	8	8	10
Day3	5	4	3	3	4	3	7	7	4
Day 7	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	4	3
Day 14	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	5	2
Day 21	3	2	2	2	2	2	2	5	2
Day 28	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	5	2

On day 0, 5/9 dogs were evaluated with PVAS 8, 3/9 dogs with PVAS 9, and 1/9 dog with PVAS 10.

On day 3, 3/9 dogs were evaluated with PVAS 3, 3/9 dogs with PVAS 4, 1/9 dog with PVAS 5, 2/9 dogs with PVAS 7.

On day 7, 6/9 dogs were evaluated with very mild itching (consider normal) PVAS 2, 2/9 were evaluated with pruritus and PVAS 3, 1/9 dog was assessed with itching on the PVAS 4.

On day 14, 8/9 dogs were evaluated with very mild itching (consider normal).

On day 21, 7/9 dog was PVAS 2, 1/9 dog is with PVAS 3 and 1/9 dog with PVAS 5.

On Day 28, 8/9 dogs were with PVAS 2 and 1/9 dog with PVAS 5.

1/9 dogs on Day 14, 21, 28 continued to experience mild to moderate itching, itching periodically throughout the day (dog did not itch when eating, playing, exercising). It received a new Lokivetmab injection (second) on day 28, but without effect. On day 56 its PVAS was 5. Topical corticosteroids (Cortavance spray, Virbac France) and oral Prednisolone (Hedylon 5 mg, Livisto, Italy) were used with great effect in reducing pruritus. This therapy provided good effect. None of the patients experienced any side effects from the administration of Lokivetmab.

Discussion

To understand why the IL-31 monoclonal antibody may be a valuable aid in the management of patients with atopic dermatitis controlled with ASIT, we need to know the role of IL-31 and the importance of antibodies against it in the control and pathogenesis of pruritus. The IL-31 as a T-cell-derived cytokine was first identified in 2004 (Dillon *et al.* 2004) and its role in the cutaneous signs and symptoms of pruritus and skin inflammation was confirmed. Overexpression of IL-31 in skin is also in connection with suppression of the filaggrin protein, which is important in the differentiation of keratinocytes and skin barrier maintenance (Cornelissen *et al.* 2012). IL-31 induces keratinocytes cell cycle arrest, resulting in reduced proliferation and skin barrier dysfunction (Cornelissen *et al.* 2012). IL-31 has been linked to hematopoiesis and regulation of the immune response (Zhang *et al.* 2008), has a key point in the acute and chronic pruritus symptoms (Gonzales *et al.* 2016) and has therefore become a potential therapeutic targets for pruritic diseases therapy Lokivetmab (ZTS-00103289) is a caninized IL-31 monoclonal antibody that has efficacy in reducing pruritus in dogs with atopic dermatitis cases (Michels *et al.* 2016, Souza *et al.* 2018, Szczepanik *et al.* 2020), and cases with mastocytosis (Meichner *et al.* 2019). Lokivetmab has the ability to neutralize IL-31, a key pruritogenic cytokine implicated in the pathogenesis of canine atopic dermatitis (AD). IL-31, produced predominantly by activated Th2 lymphocytes, binds to IL-31 receptors expressed on cutaneous sensory neurons and keratinocytes, thereby initiating and perpetuating the itch-scratch cycle characteristic of allergic skin disease. Lokivetmab binds circulating IL-31 fast with high affinity, preventing receptor activation and consequently interrupting pruritus signaling. Following subcutaneous administration, clinical improvement was reduced in pruritus and lesion severity – typically within 24 to 48 hours and persists for approximately 4 to 8 weeks. Compared with traditional antipruritic agents (e.g., glucocorticoids, cyclosporine, oclacitinib), Lokivetmab offers targeted biological modulation with a favorable safety profile, minimal hepatic or renal metabolism, and compatibility with other therapeutic modalities such as allergen-specific immunotherapy (ASIT) (Gober *et al.* 2025, Souza *et al.* 2018).

After the administration of Lokivetmab observed a rapid reduction in pruritus. On Day 3, in only 2 patients the PVAS was 7. On Day 7, 8/9 dogs were with PVAS which corresponds to the absence of pathological itching. All 9/9 patients successfully continued their ASIT protocol. In only 1/9 cases in which pruritus did not respond to Lokivetmab injection, In this patient IL-31 did not play an active key role in pruritus. In this case another molecule has a key role for pruritus. Lokivetmab clearly suppressed pruritus rapidly and potently in patients with IL-31-mediated pruritus.

Conclusion

ASIT is a reliable, safe and modern approach to the long-term management of patients with atopic dermatitis. Lokivetmab is novel target therapy agent that is indicated for the management of

IL-31 induced pruritus associated with allergic and atopic dermatitis in dogs and may serve as an adjunct to long-term immunotherapy allergy control protocols. It allows for a harmless and very rapid suppressing of itching during periods of increased symptoms in patients undergoing long-term control of AD with ASIT.

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